

INTERACTION OF HYDROXYACETOPHENONES AND THEIR
DERIVATIVES AND THIONYL CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE
OF FINELY DIVIDED COPPER. PART IX. PREPARATION
OF 3:3'-DIACETYL-4:4'-DIHYDROXY-6:6'-DIMETHYL-
DIPHENYL SULPHIDE AND 3:3'-DIACETYL-4:4'-
DIMETHYL-6:6'-DIHYDROXY-DIPHENYL
SULPHIDE AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

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Preparation of 3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide (I) and 3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dimethyl-6:6'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide (II) is described. Bromination furnishes the corresponding dibromo sulphides which on nitration yield 2-bromo-3-methyl-4:6-dinitrophenol. Nitration of both the sulphides affords 2:4:6-trinitro-3-methylphenol as the final product, but in the case of the sulphide (II) dinitrosulphide and 2-methyl-3:5-dinitro-4-hydroxy-acetophenone have also been isolated under suitable experimental conditions.

The present work is the continuation of Part VII (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 266). The sulphides (I) and (II) are obtained when 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone (6-acetyl-*m*-cresol) and 4-hydroxy-6-methylacetophenone (4-acetyl-*m*-cresol) are allowed to react with thionyl chloride in presence of copper or with sulphur dichloride or sulphur monochloride. Vigorous nitration of both yields 2:4:6-trinitro-3-methylphenol, and hence, no definite conclusion can be drawn about the constitution of the sulphides.

Bromination of (I) furnishes a compound which cannot be crystallised, but by the action of nitric acid on it 2-bromo-3-methyl-4:6-dinitrophenol is obtained. 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of the bromination product can be obtained which shows the presence of sulphur also. Out of the two nitro groups in the final bromonitrocresol, one must have come in place of the original acetyl group and the other in place of the sulphur atom joining the two nuclei. The sulphide (I) is therefore assigned the constitution 3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide. When the action of nitric acid alone is carried out on ketone (II), the 3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dimethyl-5:5'-dinitro-6:6'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide (III) is obtained, but when it is treated with nitric acid in presence of sulphuric acid, 2-methyl-3:5-dinitro-4-hydroxy-acetophenone (IV) is obtained. Nitration of (II) in presence of sulphuric acid and at higher temperature affords 2:4:6-trinitro-3-methylphenol (2:4:6-trinitro-*m*-cresol). 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones of both (III) and (IV) have been prepared.

As nitration is not useful in proving the constitution of the sulphide (II), its bromination has been carried out in presence of acetic acid which yields dibromo sulphide (V), the latter affording the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative. The sulphide (V) furnishes on nitration in presence of sulphuric acid, 2-bromo-3-methyl-4:6-dinitrophenol. One of these nitro groups has come in place of the acetyl group and the other in place of the sulphur atom linking the two nuclei. The position of the acetyl group is fixed and is at 4 with regard to the -OH group, and hence, the two nuclei must have been linked in the position-6 with regard to the -OH group. The sulphide (V) is therefore

assigned the constitution 3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dimethyl-5:5'-dibromo-6:6'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide. The sulphide (II) should therefore be 3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dimethyl-6:6'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide.

EXPERIMENTAL

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dimethyldiphenyl Sulphide (I).—This was prepared by shaking for 2 hours the mixture of 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone (6-acetyl-*m*-cresol) (3 c.c.) and thionyl chloride (3 c.c.) and adding gradually copper powder (2 g.) to it, and leaving the reaction mixture overnight at room temperature. It was then extracted with dry chloroform. The pasty mass left after removal of the solvent was again dissolved in chloroform and again the solvent was removed, when a reddish brown paste was left behind. It solidified on boiling with water for some time. Finally a yellowish solid was obtained from alcohol, m.p. 100-101°. (Found: C, 65.4; H, 6.7; S, 9.8. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4S$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5; S, 9.7 per cent).

It is very soluble in chloroform and benzene, fairly so in carbon tetrachloride, ether and acetone, and sparingly in alcohol.

The same sulphide (I) was also prepared by the interaction of the ketone (2 c.c.) and sulphur dichloride (3 c.c.) directly or in presence of chloroform (10 c.c.) or sulphur monochloride (2 c.c.), allowing the reaction to proceed overnight at room temperature.

The diacetoxy derivative of (I) was prepared by acetylating it with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine, and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 101° (decomp.). (Found: S, 7.7. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6S$ requires S, 7.3 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (I) crystallised from benzene, m.p. 124-25°. (Found: S, 4.8. $C_{20}H_{20}O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 4.6 per cent).

2:4:6-Trinitro-3-methylphenol (2:4:6-trinitro-*m*-cresol).—The sulphide (I, 1 g.) was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (15 c.c.) and fuming nitric acid (7 c.c.) was gradually added to it when a vigorous reaction took place. After about an hour, the mixture was poured over crushed ice when sticky mass separated which was filtered. The filtrate on standing overnight furnished a yellowish solid which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 108-109°. No lowering in melting point was observed when mixed with a genuine specimen.

2-Bromo-3-methyl-4:6-dinitrophenol (2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol).—The solution of the sulphide (I, 1 g.) in chloroform (20 c.c.) was treated with an excess of 20% bromine solution and the mixture was left overnight at room temperature. On removal of chloroform a red paste was obtained which could not be crystallised from any solvent. It was therefore treated with HNO_3 (conc.) in presence of H_2SO_4 at room temperature and then diluted. The yellow solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 104-105°. (Found: Br, 28.9. Calc. for $C_7H_5O_2N_2Br$: Br, 28.8 per cent). Mixed m.p. with the genuine specimen prepared by bromination in chloroform solution of 4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (m.p. 60°) from 6-nitro-*m*-cresol ($-\text{OH} = 1$) remained undepressed. Gibbs and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1889) record m.p. 104-105°.

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of the pasty bromo derivative of (I) had m.p. 90°. (Found: S, 3.6. $C_{20}H_{24}O_{10}N_2Br_2S$ requires S, 3.8 per cent).

3 : 3'-*Diacetyl-4 : 4'-dimethyl-6 : 6'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide* (II) was prepared in the same way as the sulphide (I), described above. The substance obtained from the chloroform solution was, however, extracted with alcohol and the dark brown paste obtained from alcoholic extract was boiled with water for some time when a brown solid was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 105-106°. (Found : C, 65.8 ; H, 5.2 ; S, 9.9. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4S$ requires C, 65.5 ; H, 5.5 ; S, 9.7 per cent).

This same sulphide (II) was also obtained by using sulphur dichloride or sulphur monochloride and the ketone as in the case of (I).

The *diacetoxy derivative* of (II) was prepared by acetylating (II) as in the case of the diacetoxy derivative of (I). It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 98-99°. (Found : S, 7.6. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6S$ requires S, 7.3 per cent).

2 : 4-*Dinitrophenylhydrazone* of (II) was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 125-26°. (Found : S, 4.7. $C_{20}H_{20}O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 4.6 per cent).

5 : 5'-*Dinitro derivative* of (II) i.e. (III) was obtained when (II, 1 g.) was gradually added to HNO_3 (conc., 20 c.c.) and the mixture heated on a boiling water-bath for half an hour. The yellow solid obtained on dilution was extracted with carbon disulphide and the insoluble residue was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 150-51°. (Found : S, 7.4. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8N_2S$ requires S, 7.6 per cent).

The 2 : 4-*dinitrophenylhydrazone* of (III) was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 137-38°. (Found : S, 3.9. $C_{20}H_{24}O_{14}N_{10}S$ requires S, 4.1 per cent).

2-*Methyl-3 : 5-dinitro-4-hydroxy-acetophenone* (IV).—The sulphide (II) or (III) (1 g.) was gradually added to the mixture of H_2SO_4 (20 c.c.) and HNO_3 (15 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The product obtained on dilution was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 103-104°. (Found : N, 11.5. $C_9H_8O_6N_2$ requires N, 11.7 per cent). This was found identical with the product obtained from 4-acetyl-*m*-cresol (5 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (30 c.c.), by the action of nitric acid (3 c.c.), dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.), on it and heating the mixture on a boiling water-bath for some time.

2 : 4-*Dinitrophenylhydrazone* of (IV) melted 120-21°. (Found : N, 19.6. $C_{18}H_{12}O_8N_2$ requires N, 20.0 per cent).

When nitration of (II) was carried out in presence of H_2SO_4 by heating the mixture on a boiling water-bath for 3 hours, 2 : 4-*6-trinitro-3-methylphenol*, m.p. 108-109° was obtained.

5 : 5'-*Dibromo derivative* of (II) i. e. (V) was prepared from (II, 0.5 g.), suspended in acetic acid (20 c.c.), by the action of 5% bromine solution in acetic acid (25 c.c.) on it. The mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for a few minutes and left overnight at room temperature. The product obtained on dilution crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 190-91°. (Found : S, 6.5. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4Br_2S$ requires S, 6.6 per cent).

2 : 4-*Dinitrophenylhydrazone* of (V) crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 130° (decomp.). (Found : S, 3.9. $C_{20}H_{24}O_{10}N_2Br_2S$ requires S, 3.8 per cent).

2-Bromo-3-methyl-4:6-dinitrophenol was formed when the sulphide (V, 0.05 g.) was mixed with H_2SO_4 (20 c.c.), and HNO_3 (15 c.c.) was added to it. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. The product obtained on dilution was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 104-105°. It showed no lowering in melting point when mixed with the bromodinitro-*m*-cresol, obtained by the action of nitric acid in presence of sulphuric acid on the bromo derivative of (I), described before.

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